

An Overview of Edge computing and Role of edge computing in IoT

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Abstract : As a high growth of Internet of Everything (IoE) internet connection has been increased a lot which leads to low bandwidth ,less security low privacy in cloud computing model to over come this edge computing technologies have emerged . Edge computing is an emerging paradigm which refers to a range of networks and devices near the user . Edge means processing the data closer to the end user where it's being generated, so the processing with greater speed and volumes ,which can leads to greater action results in real time. This article is going to summarizes the concept of edge computing ,architecture of edge computing and compares it with cloud computing and role of edge computing in IoT.

Keywords: edge computing, edge computing architecture , IoT , cloud computing ,edge computing databases .

Introduction :

Edge computing is a new computing model. It can be seen from the definition of edge computing that edge computing is not to replace cloud computing but to supplement cloud computing, providing a better computing platform for mobile computing and Internet of things[1]. Edge computing already exists in retail locations , hospitals , factories , which process the critical and sensitive data with more reliable and with high safety , with low latency and without internet connection . Everything in the world now a days become very smart - cities ,health ,movies , agriculture etc . In future with heavy data where billions of devices connected to the internet data processing and fast transfer of data will become crucial. When the things and the information are connected to internet is referred as Internet on things . The raise of mobile computing and IoT created strain on networking bandwidth where edge computing entered . The cloud needs to process a numerous amount of data and the physical distance between the centralised cloud and the end user

increases which leads to increase the response time and transmission latency which stress out the user .Processing speed also depends upon the performance of users device .The solution to this problem is “*EDGE COMPUTING PLATFORM* “. As per CB Insights Market Sizing tool, the global edge computing market is established to reach by 2022.[2]. Here data will be processed nearby where it is created so that transfer of data from the cloud can be reduced. According to research firm IDC.[3] International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) Edge computing “ mesh network Micro data centres processes and stores the data internally and stores all the data in cloud storage or central data centre” . Edge computing and IoT become common in our life and become an active research field for bandwidth cost saving ,data security ,data integrity and privacy. Edge computing with Internet on things can able to create smart homes, cities, health ,hospitals and smart environment .

Difference between Cloud computing and Edge computing

Cloud Computing	Edge computing
1.Data is stored in cloud	1.Data is stored in client endpoint
2.Dynamic workloads	2.Big datasets will be costly to send to cloud
3.Internet connection must be reliable	3.Any remote locations with limited or no internet connectivity
4.Non time sensitive data processing	4.Real time data processing [4]
5.Data stored in centralised location	5.Distributes data across multiple location
6.Cloud computing is more cost-effective because it centralizes resources in a single location.	6.Edge computing is less cost-effective.
7. Cloud computing lends itself more naturally to applications where large amounts of data need to be processed at once	7.Edge computing is better suited for devices that need fast connections and low latency .

Edge Computing Architecture

[5]

In the above edge computing architecture, the topmost layer is cloud data centres which has interconnected data centre and central data centre. The final repository of the information will be stored in cloud data centre, cloud data centre plays a major role in edge computing architecture. However local applications are not depends on cloud computing. The second layer of the edge computing is edge layer. This layer consists of IoT gate way and edge data centres which is going to run on local area network such as wireless , 4G , 5G and fibre cable . Within the edge layer of architecture the individual devices like tablets, laptops and smartphone used by the end users also communicate with IoT devices

with edge data centres. There might be n number of edge data centres for easy computing across a business system. For example we may use POS for chain of retail stores which are using edge data centres.

Edge Computing and Databases

When building an edge architecture, we have to focus on the database that has to be used

1. Database runs in all the layers
2. Distribution and Updation of data happens in all the layers
3. Synchronizes data change immediately in all the layers

In the above edge computing architecture, the red database icons in which the data is stored and processed. In the cloud layer the main database server is installed in the central data centre and the interconnected DC. Next in the edge layer database server is installed in the edge data centre. Even though in the network failure, the database can directly select IoT devices and edge mobile and the data will be processing continuously.

As such, in the diagram you also see data being synchronized:

In the above edge computing architecture the data is synchronized

1. Between the cloud data centre database server and edge data centre database servers
2. Between databases on devices and IoT and database servers .
3. Between the embedded databases on devices and things, using private area networks

The applications process data in the edge data centres if the internet connections to the cloud data centre stops or slows down. Apps embedded databases will process continuously even though if edge data centre and cloud data centre are not available by processing the data directly between devices. Edge devices with data processing serve as their own micro data centre to run the real time responsiveness until the connectivity is restored with data privacy and security. Edge computing refers to a new computing model that analyzes and processes a portion of data using the computing, storage, and network resources distributed on the paths between data sources and the cloud computing center (Shi et al., 2016). Edge computing focuses on real-time, short-period data analysis, close to the device side, and it is better able to support local business real-time analysis and intelligent processing.[6]

Role of computing in Internet of Things

The Strategic brain of IoT is edge computing . Edge computing will decrease service latency and it is used to reduce the amount of data sent to the cloud. In this section , several roles of edge computing with IoT will be discussed

Data Acquisition

Edge devices ,machines will capture the data for data analysis and perform the process od the data immediately by moving the algorithm to the data . so that we can prevent the product defects efficiently and increase the productivity .Immediate decision can be taken in smart transportation ,traffic light cameras capture the data and also analyse the data

Inferential Controls

Inferential controls are the main components of an edge device . These controls will communicate with the infrastructure which is also controlled by the other organisation . These controls refers the capacity of the device so that the control can interpret things accurately. In a smart transportation ,these controls

will provide the drivers with intelligent navigation instructions with the help of GPS.[8]

Data Analysis

Edge computing uses real time data analysis to reduce the latency of information generation from the data has been collected. Edge devices will collect the data from the near by devices and analyse the data and take the decision to deliver actionable insights faster .It reduces the network bandwidth and cost has the data is analysed locally .this technology is helpfu; for many organisations so that the need of the IoT concepts increases a lot . The traffic light cameras analyse the data themselves and communicate with other devices and make the decision immediately to complete the task.

Decision making

After the above process data analysing ,the edge devices has to make a strategic decisions .In a smart transportation system , every second large amount of data will be generated and edge device needs real time processing and have to make correct decision[9] .In real time processing the response time will be more if the data has to send to cloud for processing and decision making.so the data will be analysed locally on the edge device itself to make correct decision on spot .

Data Security

In edge computing data collection data analysis are performed locally so that security of the data increases. Easy to identify any security breach occurs and necessary actions can be taken and implemented.

Conclusion : In this article , we have discussed about the edge computing , difference between edge and cloud computing ,edge computing architecture . The world is moving with millions of data has to be processed and we are in the need of faster connection is being crucial .For real time processing receiving and sending the data to the cloud and get the immediate decision takes more time .The solution for the above problem is edge computing where data collection , data analysis and decision making will takes place in edge device on IoT . This technology is still in developing so it is difficult predict its success .Even though, many organisation are already using this edge computing technology

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